

THE IMPORTANCE OF INTERNET PLATFORMS IN THE CREATION OF ELECTRONIC TEXTBOOKS.

Aliyeva Nodira

a senior teacher, Tashkent University of Applied Sciences
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10082064>

Abstract. Online teaching has globally become a part of the learning process and has been more well-established in developed countries. In developing countries, online teaching or e-Learning is not practiced or recognized officially by educational organizations and policymakers. On the other hand, it is well-known that computers and technology are the future; in such a case, the advancement of distance-learning or online learning is immensely remarkable. It has reduced teachers' and students' introversion concerning e-learning and technology and has provided a platform for learning new technologies and developing new skills. The findings revealed that most teachers had negative perceptions of implementing e-learning for several reasons, including lack of essential facilities such as electricity, electronic devices, and the absence of required skills. The actual contributions of students and educators are also among the major obstacles. This research suggests introducing Information Communication Technology modules across media platforms and applications in the education departments, opening intensive courses for teachers, and developing educational facilities in the education departments and schools to overcome these limitations and challenges.

Keywords: Electronic Learning; Electronic Textbook; Individualized Active Educational Environment; Didactic Features of the E-Textbook.

Online platforms support so many of our daily activities that we have become dependent on them in our personal and professional lives. We rely on them to buy and sell goods and services, to find information online and to keep in touch with each other. We use them for entertainment, news, transportation, accommodation, finding jobs and employees, finding apps and for many other purposes. Online platforms have also raised new and important policy questions, but the businesses themselves can be more complex than they appear so they are not always well understood. This report contains detailed profiles of twelve of the world's leading platform companies and derives insights from those profiles about what platforms actually do, how they do it, and why they succeed financially. For example, the report finds that although platforms tend to have a number of economic characteristics in common, they also vary so greatly that they cannot be compartmentalised into just a few categories, let alone a single sector. Moreover, they do not all succeed for the same reasons. In addition, although the major Chinese platforms still have a low profile within the OECD, they are in the process of expanding globally and deserve more attention.

Online teaching and learning have rarely been as popular as they are now. With the advent of online teaching platforms, higher education has become more effective and efficient. Directors, principals, and deans of corporate and higher education institutions are also

embracing the transition from offline to online at a rapid pace. Over three million students have decided to trust the online mode for all higher education needs.

So, online teaching platforms have become a necessity in 2022 rather than a luxury. If your higher education institution hasn't yet shifted to online teaching/learning platforms, this article details the best reasons for you to take the plunge right now.

The country's competitiveness in the modern world is the most important criterion for the development of the state and ensuring national security. Russia is actively implementing information technologies in all spheres of society and human activity through the verification of national projects, for example, the national project "Education" is aimed at improving the competitiveness of Russian education. Russia is scheduled to enter the top ten countries in the world in terms of quality of education by 2024. One of the goals is to "create a modern and secure digital educational environment by 2024 that ensures high quality and accessibility of education of all types and levels" and "modernization of professional education". Modern university education is carried out in an information and educational environment (hereinafter – IEE), which includes such educational resources as electronic libraries, video and online courses, and electronic textbooks. An electronic textbook (hereinafter – ET) is a digital learning tool that contains a systematic and complete presentation of the subject or part of it, ensuring the completeness of the didactic cycle of the learning process, creating an individualized active educational environment. Since 2017, an information portal has been functioning that provides practical implementation of the project "Modern digital educational environment in the Russian Federation". More than 30 online educational platforms, more than 120 universities interact online, and more than 1000 registered online courses are offered. The analysis of information portals of leading Russian universities allows to state the insufficient availability of electronic textbooks that correspond to the definition of an electronic textbook, the purpose of which is to automate the control of students' knowledge, the implementation of feedback between the teacher and the student.

Methods and Materials. In recent studies, the didactic features of an electronic textbook as a source of educational content are presented. The main feature of the electronic textbook is that it includes not only the content of education, but also the selected learning technology. An electronic textbook is an automated training system that includes didactic, methodological, and informational reference materials for an academic discipline, as well as software that allows using them in a comprehensive way to obtain and control knowledge independently. Table 3 shows the features of creating an electronic textbook.

Our empirical research was conducted in specialized economic classes of Moscow universities that signed contracts with schools for admission of graduates to specific universities. Let us consider which lines of textbooks are suitable for integration with information and communication technologies and can be taken as the basis of the model of economic education. Textbooks on social science were developed by scientists and teachers of the Humanities; textbooks on Economics - by academic economists. Social science textbooks have a predominantly descriptive style of presentation. Focusing on humanist teachers, the authors of these textbooks avoid analytical (mathematical) and graphical forms of presentation of educational material. At the same time, it becomes difficult to consider macro- and microeconomic models in full: content elements, key economic concepts are given in fragments, in isolation from their connections: functional, logical, hierarchical, etc. These textbooks are insufficiently illustrated with diagrams and poorly structured, which does not

really correspond to modern economic theory. As a result, the predominance of the reproductive form, as for independent productive activity, students will have to get an idea of the objective connections of economic concepts and dependencies expressed by formulas. From the point of view of the topic of this study, it can be concluded that the imposition of ICT on such a content structure is ineffective, as it will require a lot of additional refinement. Textbooks on Economics written by economists, not teachers, are difficult for high school students to understand (note in parentheses, and for teachers of Humanities, they are also difficult); they are mostly translated, and do not take into account the peculiarities of the Russian economy. At the same time, they are well structured, which makes it possible to illustrate macro - and micro-economic models, their elements and main connections with the help of modern multimedia; they represent the material both in analytical and graphical form. This construction of economic content could provide an activity approach, but, as shown above, does not implement it. The content structure of such textbooks, in our opinion, is more consistent with the architecture of an electronic textbook, which involves the use of multimedia and hypertext, splitting the content into separate modules without violating the logic of studying the content.

A wide range of work with students, an optimization of the educational process, a wide range of illustrative opportunities, the development of learning activities, quick and effective control, and the didactical advantages of e-textbooks as a source of educational information are just a few of the ways that information and communication technologies have a high potential for pedagogy. ICT has many benefits, but it also has drawbacks, such as loss of control over a strategic resource (economic education content), decline in the quality of educational resources available, infringement on the teacher's monopoly in the classroom, etc. The researchers claim that the selection of the priority model for education determines the extent and efficacy of ICT use in education.

Results and Discussion .What is an Online Teaching Platform?

An online teaching platform facilitates the smooth transfer of educational content between teachers and students. Online teaching platforms enable access to information through videos, audio, PowerPoint presentations, PDFs, brochures, bite-sized content, and whatnot. As the stakeholder (read: director, principal, or dean) of a higher education institution, you can use such platforms to ensure high-quality education.

The future of higher education will be dominated by technology. Modern online teaching platforms integrate the best practices of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) to make training more impactful for students and more result-driven for teachers.

The following sections discuss the top benefits of online teaching platforms for the stakeholders of general and professional higher education institutions.

Proven Benefits of Online Teaching Platforms for Higher Educational Institutions

1. Extraordinary Reach

We have moved far away from the times when education delivery was location-specific. The proliferation of digital media, digital devices, and the rise of the World Wide Web (WWW) has brought education to the learners' fingertips. Online teaching platforms provide higher education institutions with the right interface to connect with learners and distribute their knowledge.

An online teaching platform helps you expand your reach and achieve remarkable growth. You can simply create an account, upload some content, and market it through social media or

other channels. Once the learners find value in the content delivered by your teachers, they will rush to you to quench their interest in quality knowledge.

Some teachers may or may not have a full-time job in hand. Whatever the case may be, online teaching platforms give them an excellent opportunity to make some extra money in their free time. Once they identify their forte, they can spread their knowledge among the audience. And, as the key stakeholder of a higher education institution, you can use their popularity to publicize your brand.

Some teaching platforms also facilitate the smooth processing of the course fee and provide you with a report of who has paid and who hasn't. You can quickly look up the list and follow up with the learners who haven't paid.

Unlike a traditional classroom, online teaching platforms make student management super easy. Since online classrooms are typically access-based and password-protected, you can withdraw access from non-paid students and ask them to pay soon to continue receiving the training materials.

Hence, online teaching platforms take away the mundane tasks of fee management and let your teachers focus on what they excel in – teaching.

3. Better ROI

Return on Investment (ROI) is a key driver of business success. While physical infrastructure is definitely required to a certain extent, the pandemic and its after-effects have reaffirmed the need for designing an efficient digital ecosystem. Fortunately, the cost of setting up a digital training delivery mechanism is much easier than setting up a training facility with physical infrastructure.

Online teaching platforms eliminate the need to rent or buy a space for training, pay electricity bills, print training materials, and the like. Moreover, you and the trainers do not need to travel to and fro the institute to deliver quality training. This can enable higher savings for trainers, students, and educational institutions. Moreover, unlike physical classrooms, the teachers do not need to deliver demo lectures since the recorded video lectures can serve the purpose easily.

Flexibility Reigns Supreme

The COVID-19 pandemic has wreaked havoc on human life and income. To offset the damage caused by the pandemic-led economic slowdown, most professionals are taking up some extra workload to sustain themselves. However, more work means less time to study.

Online teaching platforms ensure that learning never succumbs to the pressure of time. Both teachers and students can choose a convenient time to get on board and deliver or receive quality training. Alternatively, online teaching platforms allow cloud-based video storage and automatic playlist creation.

Optimize Time. In the modern world, time equals money. Unlike conventional classrooms, online teaching platforms ensure time and cost-saving. Once the teachers of your institution design and create the training resources, you are ready to publish them whenever you want and as many times as you want.

Hence, online teaching platforms let you utilize your time to the fullest and reduce time wastage.

Conclusion. A wide range of work with students, an optimization of the educational process, a wide range of illustrative opportunities, the development of learning activities, quick and effective control, and the didactical advantages of e-textbooks as a source of educational

information are just a few of the ways that information and communication technologies have a high potential for pedagogy. ICT has many benefits, but it also has drawbacks, such as loss of control over a strategic resource (economic education content), decline in the quality of educational resources available, infringement on the teacher's monopoly in the classroom, etc. The researchers claim that the selection of the priority model for education determines the extent and efficacy of ICT use in education.

References:

1. Abuzjarova, M.I. (2018). Tendencies, law of development and economic content of innovative entrepreneurship. *Modern Economy Success*, (1), 43-50.
2. Aminova, D. K., & Tsakhaeva, A. A. (2018). Effective preparation of the future psychologist as one of the elements of the security education system. *International Journal of Medicine and Psychology*, 1(3), 40 – 47.
3. Ashmarov, I.A. (2018). Some approaches to the study of the USSR' military economy in the soviet and russian national historiography. *Historical Bulletin*, 1(2), 19 – 31.
4. Badakhova, I.T. (2017). Formation of professionally significant qualities of future managers in the training process forming. *Modern Scientist*, (7), 81 – 84.
5. Bolotin, I.S., Mikhaylov, A.A., & Sorokina, N.D. (2017). Functional literacy of students in terms of introduction of information technologies (on the example of research among the students of MAI). *Modern Scientist*, 1(1), 160–163.
6. Borisov, V.I. (2018). Influence of the food crisis for the revolution of the working mass of russia in the years of the first world war (August 1914 - February 1917). *Historical Bulletin*, 1 (2), 49 – 55.
7. Borisova, M.V., Musokhranov, A.Yu., Sidorova N.A. (2018). Use of fitness directions elements on physical education classes and their psychomatic impact on students of the special medical group. *Modern Scientist*, (1), 6 – 9.
8. Borovikova, T.V. (2017). Methodological bases of formation of the intellectual potential of territories in the conditions of innovative economy. *Modern Economy Success*, (6), 46 – 49.
9. Bugreeva, A.S. (2019). Questions of efficiency of using digital technologies in the system of higher vocational education. *Modern Scientist*, (6), 86 – 91.
10. Filippova, E.O., Marchenko, L.O., & Levich, S.N. (2019). The role of intellectual abilities at the stage of professional training selection. *Modern Scientist*, (5), 39 – 45.
11. Gadzaov, A.F., & Dzerzhinskaya, M.R. (2018). Mathematical methods of analysis of the periodic components of economic processes. *Modern Economy Success*, (1), 14 – 18.
12. Gadzhieva, U.B. (2018). Socialization of personality as a factor in the mental, intellectual and spiritual-moral development. *International Journal of Medicine and Psychology*, 1(Issue 2), 7 – 20.
13. Gasanova, P.G., Daudova, D.M, Kabieva, R.A., & Tsahaeva, A.A. (2017). Moral qualities of businessmen in public con-sciousness. *Modern Scientist*, 1(1), 209 – 211.
14. Gnatyuk, S.N., & Pekert, N.A. (2018). Education as a factor of sustainable development of agriculture. *Russian Economic Bulletin*, 1(3), 18 – 27.
15. Korotkov, S.L. (2019). Interdisciplinary approach to the learning process. *Modern Scientist*, (5), 18 – 23.
- Kryuchkova, K.S. (2018) Modular training of future teachers with the use of

information technologies in the conditions of virtual academic mobility. Modern Humanities Success, 2(4), 9 – 14.

16.Kuznetsov, A.A., Ignatyeva, T.A., & Kuznetsov, A.O. (2018). Strategy and key elements of competitiveness. Modern Economy Success, (1), 25 – 29.

